

1

2

3 THIS PAPER WAS ACCEPTED TO THE JOURNAL OF THE ATMOSPHERIC SCIENCES ON 6/18/2026

4 **Shear-Driven Instabilities as the Origin of Multi-Banded Cloud and**
5 **Precipitation Structures in an Extratropical Cyclone**

6 Stephen R. Guimond^a

7 ^a *Department of Atmospheric and Planetary Sciences and Severe Weather Research Center,*
8 *Hampton University, Hampton, VA, USA*

9 *Corresponding author:* Stephen R. Guimond, stephen.guimond@hamptonu.edu

10 ABSTRACT: This paper investigates the dynamics governing multi-banded cloud and precipitation
11 in extratropical cyclones through a case study from the NASA Investigation of Microphysics
12 and Precipitation for Atlantic Coast-Threatening Snowstorms (IMPACTS) field campaign. On 1
13 February 2020, a low-pressure system emerged off the North Carolina coast at 1200 UTC, deepening
14 by 7 hPa in six hours as it accelerated northeast over the Atlantic. High-resolution GOES visible
15 imagery revealed multiple bands of high-reflectance cloud to the north/northeast of the center, along
16 with clusters of convective cells closer to the core. Wavelet analysis identified a dominant multi-
17 band wavelength of 30 km and a secondary peak at 15-20 km. Airborne radar measurements from
18 IMPACTS flights showed deep convection near the center and narrow, elevated reflectivity bands
19 linked to the multi-band features farther out. Numerical simulations reproduced the multi-bands,
20 enabling exploration of their dynamical origin. Intrinsic phase speed and polarization relation
21 calculations revealed that, contrary to several previous studies, the dominant multi-bands were not
22 gravity waves. Instead, the bands were identified as manifestations of inflection-point instability
23 due to the presence of counter-rotating secondary circulations and the vertical wind shear profile
24 with low Richardson numbers near the upper-level outflow. Gravity waves were present in the
25 low-to-mid levels generated by convection, but they did not account for the strong perturbations in
26 the mid-to-upper levels. These new scientific insights into the governing dynamics of multi-banded
27 structures in extratropical cyclones highlight the role of shear-driven, hydrodynamic instabilities.

28 SIGNIFICANCE STATEMENT: Extratropical cyclones along the United States East Coast can
29 produce intense bands of snow and other types of precipitation that cause travel chaos and potential
30 loss of life. In this work, a storm of this type was studied using NASA aircraft and satellite
31 data as well as computer simulations. The results show that the storm bands were not caused by
32 atmospheric waves, as scientists often thought, but by sharp changes in the wind speed with height
33 called shear. This shear created unstable layers that rolled and mixed the air, forming organized
34 cloud and precipitation patterns. Understanding these fundamental physical processes can help
35 forecasters better predict when and where heavy snow bands will form, improving warnings and
36 securing public safety.

37 1. Introduction

38 Banded structures in extreme weather systems are perturbations to a balanced, background
39 flow that can organize and concentrate variables such as moisture, momentum, and energy. In
40 extratropical cyclones (ETCs), the concentration of these variables can lead to intense bands of
41 multi-phase (rain, sleet, snow or some combination) precipitation at the surface that are difficult
42 to measure, model, and predict, with significant consequences for society. For example, snowfall
43 associated with ETCs in the winter months can often organize into multiple bands that drop large
44 amounts of snow in a short time causing vehicle crashes and shutdowns of schools and businesses.
45 At higher altitudes these bands can produce significant turbulence that can affect the aviation
46 industry. The current understanding of the dynamical processes controlling the formation and
47 evolution of these precipitation multi-bands (as opposed to a single, large-scale band) and their
48 representation/predictability in numerical models is very limited. These limitations were part of
49 the motivating factors for the recently completed Investigation of Microphysics and Precipitation
50 for Atlantic Coast-Threatening Snowstorms (IMPACTS; McMurdie and Coauthors 2022) field
51 experiment, which sought to improve the understanding of precipitation multi-bands in ETCs from
52 various perspectives.

53 Ganetis et al. (2018) used radar observations, soundings, and reanalysis data to examine the
54 environments containing banded structures in a large set of ETC winter storms. They found
55 that multi-bands were not well correlated with frontogenetical forcing and associated deformation
56 zones. This result is consistent with the notion that deformation alone cannot explain the regular,

57 oscillatory nature of the various fields connected to multi-bands. The authors also examined
58 the presence of conditional symmetric instability (CSI) in the environment of various types of
59 banded structures. While CSI was present in the vast majority of banded cases, there was no clear
60 separation between single, large-scale bands and the smaller-scale, multi-band structures. This
61 suggests that CSI may not be the fundamental property underlying the formation and evolution of
62 multi-bands.

63 In their review paper, Schultz and Schumacher (1999) noted that the banding of clouds and
64 precipitation in ETCs appears to be weakly related to CSI. Xu (1989) used a viscous form of
65 the Sawyer-Eliassen equation to understand banding mechanisms associated with frontogenetical
66 forcing. For broad forcing and negative moist potential vorticity, which is a condition that reflects
67 the presence of CSI, multiple bands develop with an intensity that scales with the degree of
68 instability. Xu (1992) used a viscous semigeostrophic model to study frontal rainbands and
69 proposed that multi-bands can be generated internally by a positive feedback between the moist
70 circulation bands and geostrophic forcing anomalies in association with the generation of mesoscale
71 potential vorticity anomalies.

72 The theoretical framework proposed by Xu (1989) and Xu (1992) does not clearly elucidate
73 the mechanism by which CSI produces the regularly spaced bands of clouds and precipitation
74 observed in the real atmosphere, given that CSI is a parcel instability rather than a wave instability.
75 In particular, the “positive feedback mechanism” to explain the development of multi-bands in the
76 presence of CSI is not articulated. From our viewpoint, initial oscillations in ascent are needed to
77 produce multi-bands with a regular wavelength, and the mechanism for the ascent would be the
78 fundamental driving force for the bands. The CSI, if present, would only accentuate this initial
79 ascent, but would not be the fundamental driver of the bands.

80 Another possible culprit for multi-bands is the presence of a wave phenomenon to organize the
81 oscillations in the state variables and provide the lift necessary to release any type of instability
82 in the environment. Several previous studies have focused on the role of gravity waves as the
83 mechanism for organizing the cloud and precipitation fields into multi-band structures in ETCs
84 (e.g., Bosart et al. 1998; Koch and Siedlarz 1999; Ruppert et al. 2022). These waves can be
85 generated from flow imbalances (e.g., associated with upper-level jets), convective perturbations,
86 and/or flow over topography. Koch and Siedlarz (1999) documented large-amplitude mesoscale

87 gravity waves (wavelengths of 200 - 260 km) during several winter storms using time series of
88 surface pressure and wind measurements. These gravity waves were found to originate at upper
89 levels from jet streak imbalances and the associated geostrophic adjustment process (e.g., Uccellini
90 and Koch 1987). For large-amplitude waves, a surface reflection of the upper-level perturbation
91 energy was detected and hypothesized to become trapped at lower-levels due to strong static stability
92 (“wave ducting”; Lindzen and Tung 1976). This wave ducting allows for a longer residence time of
93 the gravity wave energy in the lower levels of the atmosphere resulting in the potential for organized
94 clouds and precipitation.

95 Zhang et al. (2001) also highlighted the role of mesoscale (~ 200 km) gravity waves using
96 numerical simulations of an ETC. The authors proposed a conceptual model for the generation and
97 evolution of mesoscale gravity waves based on these simulations. First, the waves were initiated
98 in the upper levels of the system from the geostrophic adjustment process. Then, convection
99 associated with the frontal features and local instability transported some of the gravity wave
100 energy towards the surface where it can be ducted within a statically stable layer. This ducted wave
101 then interacts with the moisture field to create a convectively-coupled wave that can be maintained
102 and possibly amplified over a period of time.

103 Several questions and uncertainties come to mind regarding the applicability of these previous
104 gravity wave studies to the general problem of ETC multi-bands. How does convective activity
105 preferentially transport the wave energy initiated at upper levels (near the tropopause) downward
106 to low levels and keep the wave intact? The presence of a strong static stability layer at lower
107 levels and reflecting layer above to enable wave ducting appears to be a special set of circumstances
108 and it is not clear how this layer can be formed and maintained in regions of the system that
109 are convectively active. These questions regarding gravity waves and their overall role in ETC
110 multi-bands helped to shape the research presented in this paper.

111 The goals of the present study are: (1) To determine the key structures and spatial/temporal scales
112 of multi-banded precipitation features in ETCs and (2) To determine the origin and dynamical
113 processes associated with these bands. To address these goals, a case study from the NASA
114 IMPACTS field campaign is analyzed with multi-scale numerical simulations and a variety of
115 remote sensing measurements. Case studies are an important first step towards developing a deep,
116 holistic understanding of a physical process, which then allows that understanding to be tested

117 more broadly on a larger collection of systems. The technical novelties of the present work are in
118 the study of modern remote sensing measurements and numerical models along with some new
119 methods of analysis to the problem of ETC multi-bands.

120 **2. Brief overview of extratropical system**

FIG. 1. Synoptic maps of mean sea level pressure and frontal analysis on 1 February, 2020 at (a) 1200 UTC and (b) 1800 UTC. The figures are courtesy of the Weather Prediction Center.

121 During the winter of 2020, NASA organized the first phase of a multi-year effort called IMPACTS
122 to study the microphysics and dynamics of ETCs with a focus on understanding banded regions of
123 precipitation. On 1 February 2020, a double surface low-pressure system along a stationary front
124 formed off the coast of the Carolinas with the southern low starting off at ~ 1006 hPa on 1200 UTC
125 1 February (Fig.1a). During the next 6 hours, the southern low intensified to 999 hPa at 1800 UTC
126 1 February (Fig.1b) and to 998 hPa at 0000 UTC 2 February (not shown). Flights from the NASA
127 P-3 and ER-2 aircraft occurred during ~ 1200 - 1800 UTC 1 February sampling the environment

128 and banded features associated with the southern low. This southern low-pressure system is the
129 main focus of this paper. Figure 2 shows a large-scale, visible satellite image of the system on
130 February 1, 2020 at 1440 UTC along with a flight segment from the ER-2 aircraft that sampled the
131 convective bands. Multiple clusters of convective clouds and banded features, including associated
132 precipitation, are located to the north and northeast of the southern low-pressure center, which
133 allowed detailed study of their characteristics. These details, as well as the larger-scale structure
134 of the southern ETC, will be outlined in subsequent sections when presenting the remote sensing
135 measurements and model fields.

136 FIG. 2. GOES-16 large-scale visible satellite image on 1 February, 2020 at 1440 UTC. The red line marks
137 the track of the NASA ER-2 aircraft during the 1429 - 1449 UTC time period and the red circle denotes the
138 approximate system center.

139 3. Data and processing

140 a. EXRAD

141 The ER-2 X-band Doppler Radar (EXRAD) is an X-band, downward-pointing airborne radar
142 that measures radar reflectivity and Doppler velocity from hydrometeors with two beams and ~ 20
143 m gate spacing. The first beam is fixed and points nominally at nadir, while the second beam scans
144 conically at 20 revolutions per minute at a nominal incidence angle of 32° . From the altitude of
145 the NASA ER-2 aircraft (~ 20 km), the swath width at the first level of useful data is ~ 23 km.
146 The EXRAD scanning beam main- and side-lobes interact strongly with the ocean surface and
147 contaminate the precipitation signal below about 1 km height. The sampling of precipitation from
148 the scanning beam is ~ 500 m along-track and $\sim 2^\circ$ in azimuth while the nadir beam along-track
149 sampling is ~ 50 m.

150 Calculations of the three-dimensional (3D) wind field using the EXRAD scanning beam are
151 performed using the 3D variational algorithm described in Guimond et al. (2014). The retrieval
152 grid is set to 500 m in the horizontal dimensions and 250 m in the vertical dimension. Finer grid
153 spacing in the vertical is possible, but was not deemed necessary. A two to three grid point running
154 mean filter is applied to the raw retrievals in post-processing to remove numerical noise. The
155 effective resolution of the wind fields produced from the algorithm has been analyzed with large
156 eddy simulations in Guimond et al. (2018). Results show that scales of $5 \Delta x$ and larger are fully
157 resolved, which translates to 2.5 km for the present study. Scales below this threshold, down to the
158 grid scale, are subject to increasing kinetic energy attenuation.

159 Quality control has been performed on the wind fields to remove data with low signal-to-noise
160 ratios and high uncertainties. While a combination of parameters have been studied, the best quality
161 fields were found by removing data with standard deviations larger than 6 m/s (error statistics are
162 computed as part of the wind algorithm, see Guimond et al. (2014)). The data presented in this
163 paper have this threshold applied. Validation of the EXRAD 3D winds with flight level in-situ data
164 from the NASA P3 aircraft during IMPACTS 2020 have been performed. This validation showed
165 zonal wind root mean square errors (RMSEs) of 3.99 m/s with a correlation coefficient of 0.92. For
166 the meridional wind, the RMSEs are 4.53 m/s with a correlation coefficient of 0.89. While these
167 RMSEs may seem large, it is important to keep in mind that these statistics are collected at various

168 locations across the radar swath, which have generally larger errors away from nadir (Guimond
 169 et al. 2014), and for different time offsets ($\sim 50 - 500$ seconds). Given these complications, the
 170 EXRAD 3D winds validate reasonably well with the flight level data. Further information about
 171 these error statistics and the EXRAD scanning beam wind retrievals can be found in Guimond
 172 et al. (2014) and Guimond (2023).

173 For scientific analysis, the EXRAD scanning beam is used to present the horizontal wind field,
 174 while the nadir beam is used to display the vertical wind field, since it has higher quality. Several
 175 corrections to the nadir beam Doppler velocities are needed before the vertical velocity can be
 176 analyzed for science. The expression for the nadir beam Doppler velocity (V_d) is given by

$$V_d = \vec{V}_w \cdot \hat{e} - \vec{V}_g \cdot \hat{e} + V_n \quad (1)$$

177 where $\hat{e} = \frac{x\hat{i} + y\hat{j} + z\hat{k}}{r}$ and

$$\vec{V}_w = u\hat{i} + v\hat{j} + (w + v_t)\hat{k}, \quad (2)$$

$$\vec{V}_g = (GS_h * \sin T)\hat{i} + (GS_h * \cos T)\hat{j} + (GS_v)\hat{k} \quad (3)$$

178 and V_n represents the effects of non-uniform beam filling.

179 In these equations x, y, z are the Earth-relative coordinates of the radar pulse volumes (Guimond
 180 et al. 2014), r is the range, u, v, w are the components of the Earth-relative wind, v_t is the hydrometeor
 181 fallspeed, GS_h, GS_v are the horizontal and vertical components of the aircraft ground speed and T
 182 is the aircraft track angle.

183 Solving for the vertical velocity yields,

$$w = \frac{((V_d - V_n + \vec{V}_g \cdot \hat{e})r - ux - vy)}{z} - v_t. \quad (4)$$

184 The calculation of hydrometeor fallspeeds from the reflectivity measurements follows the studies
 185 of Ulbrich and Chilson (1994) and Heymsfield et al. (2009). The non-uniform beam filling effects
 186 are removed from the Doppler velocities following Walker McLinden et al. (2021). Aircraft motion
 187 can result in antenna pointing angles that intercept the horizontal wind field, contaminating the

188 vertical winds. The horizontal wind fields computed from the EXRAD scanning beam, described
189 above, are used to remove this contamination from the nadir beam following Eq. (4).

190 *b. GOES-16*

191 High spatial and temporal resolution imagery of clouds from the advanced baseline imager on
192 the Geostationary Operational Environmental Satellite (GOES) - 16 satellite at visible and infrared
193 wavelengths are used to track banded structures. Specifically, reflectance data from the visible
194 (channel 2) band at 500 m pixel spacing and 60 s time updates is utilized. This fine sampling in
195 space and time provides the detailed structure of the cloud lifecycle as well as the organization and
196 evolution into multi-bands.

197 *c. Numerical Simulations*

198 The Weather Research and Forecasting (WRF) model version 4.2 with the advanced research
199 dynamical core is utilized to provide context for the observations. Four domains are utilized with a
200 large, parent domain at 2 km grid spacing (domain 1; 874×883 horizontal grid points) covering the
201 full movement of the low-pressure system and banded features on 1 February 2020. Three nested
202 domains (one-way nesting) at 0.667 km (domain 2; 919×919), 0.222 km (domain 3; 1246×1246)
203 and 0.074 km (domain 4; 1801×1801) grid spacing were placed to the north and northeast of the
204 low center to try and capture the finer scales of the multi-bands. All domains utilize 121 stretched
205 vertical levels with a spacing of ~ 75 m at the surface, ~ 200 m at 10 km height and ~ 900 m near
206 the model top at 20 km height.

210 Portions of the multi-bands were captured in domains 2 and 3, but not domain 4. The focus of
211 the paper is on domain 1 for two reasons. First, this domain captures the entirety of the system,
212 which allows both large-scale and mesoscale features to be analyzed. Second, the higher resolution
213 domains were analyzed as part of this research, but they did not show a fundamental difference in
214 the multi-band structure relative to domain 1. The wavelengths of dominant features found in the
215 observations are 15-20 km and ~ 30 km, which should be well resolved by the 2 km domain given
216 the $\sim 7 - 8 \Delta x$ numerical dissipation range of WRF (e.g., Guimond et al. 2016).

217 The setup of the model is as follows. The NCEP Global Data Assimilation System (GDAS)/Final
218 (FNL) operational global analyses at 0.25° spacing and 6 h temporal spacing are used as the initial

207 FIG. 3. Configuration of the WRF simulation domains overlaid on the near-surface model reflectivity (dBZ)
 208 on February 1, 2020 at 1500 UTC for domain 1. The white, red and black boxes denote domains 2, 3 and 4,
 209 respectively.

219 and boundary conditions for the simulation. This widely used system combines the Global Forecast
 220 System (GFS) model with various synoptic-scale observations to achieve an optimal state of the
 221 atmosphere. For the 2 km parent domain the following sub-grid physics schemes were chosen:
 222 Thompson for microphysics, YSU for boundary layer (vertical diffusion), Smagorinsky-2D for
 223 horizontal diffusion, bulk aerodynamic method for surface layer fluxes and the rapid radiative
 224 transfer model for shortwave and longwave processes. A sponge layer is utilized on the upper 3 km
 225 of the domain to absorb upward propagating gravity wave energy. All other domains used the same
 226 physics schemes except for domain 4. Domain 4 does not utilize a boundary layer scheme (the grid
 227 spacing permits large turbulent eddies) and Smagorinsky-2D is replaced with Smagorinsky-3D for
 228 sub-grid turbulence. Details on the WRF modeling system including descriptions of the physical
 229 parameterizations and associated references can be found in Skamarock et al. (2019).

230 The simulations are initialized on January 31, 2020 at 00 UTC and extend out to February 2,
 231 2020 at 00 UTC. This time period covers the intensification of the southern low-pressure system

232 over the Atlantic Ocean and the evolution of a series of multi-bands. Note that storm centers for
233 the southern low-pressure system are found using the NCEP GDAS/FNL output every 6 h. The
234 sea level pressure field is filtered and the minimum pressure is used as the best guess for the storm
235 center along with checks of the vector winds to identify a circulation centroid. These storm centers
236 were found to be reasonably accurate based on airborne radar wind retrievals of the flow structure,
237 and are used as a reference point for the modeling and observational analyses.

238 **4. Remote sensing observations of multi-bands**

245 Figure 4 shows four snapshots of the multi-bands from GOES-16 visible imagery covering a 1
246 hour period (1440 - 1540 UTC) on 1 February, 2020. The multi-bands can be seen as striations
247 in the cloud reflectance most notably along the 45° azimuth in Figs. 4a - 4d, but also along the
248 90° - 100° azimuth range. As time progresses, the striations in the cloud reflectance become
249 more well-defined with an apparent regular oscillation. By 1540 UTC (Fig. 4d), the bands have
250 essentially covered the full northeast sector of the storm from $\sim 15^\circ$ to 115° and from near the storm
251 center out to at least 250 km radius. The middle of this azimuth range is in the direction of the
252 storm motion and vertical wind shear vectors. The cloud top heights derived from the GOES-16
253 infrared channel (not shown) indicate that the multi-bands presented in Fig. 4 are active in the 6 -
254 10 km height layer.

258 Figure 5 shows a vertical cross section of the EXRAD nadir beam radar reflectivity and vertical
259 velocity along the red line in Fig. 4a, which cuts through the multi-band cloud features. In the
260 reflectivity field (Fig. 5a), a series of convective plumes are evident that reach up to 8 - 10 km
261 height with the most vigorous convection located closer to the system center (around 25 km along
262 track). This deep convective cell has large reflectivity values at lower levels that extend upwards
263 through the bright band into the mid levels and above. In contrast, most of the other plumes
264 are not well connected through a deep layer, especially those highlighted above the black, dashed
265 rectangle. In this region, a clear reduction in reflectivity values is present with higher values below
266 ~ 3 km and above ~ 5 km in the plumes. The corresponding vertical velocity field in the black,
267 dashed rectangle shows a wide region of descent of several meters per second along with strong
268 regions of ascent in the cores of the convective plumes aloft. These observations indicate that the
269 plumes are not connected to the surface, but instead are most active within the 5–10 km (or 6–10

239 FIG. 4. GOES-16 visible images of multi-band cloud features in the southern low-pressure system on 1
 240 February, 2020 at (a) 1440 UTC, (b) 1510 UTC, (c) 1525 UTC, and (d) 1540 UTC. The data is shown on a
 241 storm-centered polar grid with range rings starting at 50 km and ending at 300 km. Note that 0° is pointing to
 242 the east. The red line marks the approximate track of the ER-2 aircraft during the 1429 - 1449 UTC time period
 243 (see Fig. 2 for a large-scale reference of this track). The start point of the aircraft track is near $r = 50$ km. The
 244 positive cross-track direction is from left to right across the red line looking down the track.

270 km) altitude range. This is consistent with the satellite observations of the multi-bands. The deep
 271 convection centered at ~ 25 km along track has strong updrafts at lower levels that extend upward
 272 into the mid to upper levels.

278 Figure 6 shows a vertical cross section of the EXRAD scanning beam horizontal winds in the

255 FIG. 5. EXRAD nadir beam vertical cross sections of (a) radar reflectivity (dBZ) and (b) vertical velocity
 256 (m/s) on 1 February, 2020 from 1429 - 1449 UTC. The vertical cross section is taken along the red line in Fig.
 257 4a. The black, dashed rectangle highlights a region discussed in the text.

279 same region as Fig. 5, only the data is averaged ± 5 km across track to show a bit more coverage.
 280 The along-track and across-track winds are shown in Fig. 6 because they represent the natural
 281 coordinate system of the multi-bands. The along-track and across-track winds also have some
 282 similarities to the radial and tangential winds, respectively, of the system given the orientation of
 283 the aircraft track as shown in Fig. 4a.

284 The along-track winds (Fig. 6a) show all positive values (pointing down track) that increase
 285 sharply with height indicating strong vertical wind shear is present. The across-track winds (Fig.
 286 6b) have a much more gradual change with height at low levels, but increase sharply in the plumes
 287 between $\sim 5 - 8$ km height. The low level flow is negative (pointing into the page) while the upper
 288 level flow is positive (pointing out of the page). A series of mid-level oscillations in the across-track
 289 winds are highlighted in Fig. 6b with black arrows that appear connected to the spacing of the
 290 plumes. The observed along-track and across-track winds shown in Fig. 6 will be referenced later
 291 when discussing the model simulations and their depiction of the multi-bands.

292 To determine the scale of the multi-bands, wavelet analysis was conducted on the GOES-16

273 FIG. 6. EXRAD scanning beam vertical cross sections on 1 February, 2020 1429 - 1449 UTC showing (a)
 274 along-track velocity (m s^{-1}) overlaid with vertical wind shear (positive values in white and negative values in
 275 black; s^{-1}) and (b) across-track velocity (m s^{-1}). The data is averaged ± 5 km across-track and a 5 km running
 276 mean filter is applied to the fields in the along-track direction. The vertical cross section is taken along the red
 277 line in Fig.4a. The black arrows in panel (b) point to oscillations in the across-track velocity field.

293 visible imagery. Wavelet analysis is a localized method for processing a complicated signal and
 294 extracting information on the fundamental properties of that signal (amplitude, phase, wavelength)
 295 and how those properties evolve in time or space. The GOES data is processed with a continuous
 296 wavelet transform using a Morlet mother wavelet following the methodology of Torrence and
 297 Compo (1998) and Protzko et al. (2023). GOES reflectance data is interpolated to a 100 km
 298 wide track-relative grid with the center line lying approximately along the red line denoted in Fig.
 299 4a. This track-relative grid provides a more perpendicular viewing angle of the bands for wavelet
 300 analysis.

301 The data on the track-relative grid is averaged across-track to obtain a more robust sample and

312 FIG. 7. Wavelet images corresponding to the averaged track-relative GOES reflectance data described in the
 313 text. The panels show images on 1 February, 2020 at (a) 1440 UTC, (b) 1510 UTC, (c) 1525 UTC, and (d) 1540
 314 UTC. The colors show normalized power as defined in the text. The pink, dashed lines in each panel denote the
 315 cone of influence or COI where data outside this region is more uncertain. The overlaid white contours highlight
 316 the 95% confidence level for the normalized power. The estimated lag-1 coefficient used in the significant testing
 317 is listed above each image.

302 this signal is normalized before the wavelet analysis is performed: $Y = (X - \bar{X})/\sigma(X)$, where X
 303 is the input signal, the overbar is the mean, and σ is the standard deviation. The normalized
 304 data is then fit to the AR1 (lag-1 autoregressive with Gaussian white noise) model described in
 305 Torrence and Compo (1998) to estimate the lag-1 coefficient and standard deviation parameters of
 306 the model. Following Torrence and Compo (1998), the lag-1 coefficient is used to determine the
 307 95% confidence level for a red-noise process. After the wavelet analysis is performed, the averaged
 308 power (P , dimensionless) is divided by the wavelet scale to remove the bias inherent to larger
 309 wavelengths (Liu et al. 2007), $P = |W_n(s)|^2/s$, where $W_n(s)$ is the complex wavelet transform for
 310 localized spatial index n and wavelet scale s . Further details on the wavelet analysis methodology
 311 is provided in Protzko et al. (2023).

318 Figure 7 shows wavelet images of the multi-bands (found in the $\sim 6 - 10$ km height layer) at
 319 four time intervals corresponding to the GOES images shown in Fig. 4. The dominant power in
 320 all panels is occurring at a central wavelength of ~ 30 km, which represents the main scale of the
 321 multi-bands. The core of the multi-bands is located at ~ 150 km along-track (Fig. 7a), then moves
 322 progressively down track to ~ 200 km (Fig. 7b) and ~ 225 km (Fig. 7c and Fig. 7d). During this

323 propagation down the track, the intensity of the multi-bands becomes weaker as the normalized
324 power falls from near 0.8 in Fig. 7a and Fig. 7b to about 0.4 in Fig. 7c and Fig. 7d.

325 A secondary peak in power is also evident in the vicinity of the dominant multi-bands with a
326 central wavelength of 15-20 km. These smaller-scale bands have a shorter lifetime compared to the
327 main bands and can grow or decay on the order of 30 minutes, which indicates they are convective
328 in origin. In Fig. 7a a secondary peak of power with a wavelength of 15 - 20 km is centered
329 around 200 km along-track. This feature is advected down stream to ~ 300 km along-track while
330 dissipating significantly in 30 minutes as shown in Fig. 7b. A new band is forming near 100 km
331 along-track at 1510 UTC (Fig. 7b) that intensifies and moves to 125 km along-track at 1525 UTC
332 (Fig. 7c) and then dissipates/merges with the larger scale multi-bands by 1540 UTC (Fig. 7d).
333 This sequence of wavelet images shows the life cycle of small-scale convective bands and their
334 interaction with the larger, dominant scale of the multi-bands.

335 **5. Simulated structure of multi-bands**

336 It is worthwhile to conduct a limited validation of the numerical simulation with observations
337 before analyzing the data to address the scientific goals of the study. The convective multi-bands
338 shown in Figs. 4 and 5 are in general not deterministic because of their small spatial scale
339 and sensitivity to small errors in the initial conditions. Therefore, we do not expect the model
340 simulations to reproduce the bands at the same time, same location and with the same details as
341 the observations. However, in order for the simulations to be successful, they should re-produce
342 some reasonable multi-band structure within a reasonable space/time window of the observations.

346 Figure 8 shows vertical cross sections of simulated reflectivity and vertical velocity (domain 1)
347 on 1 February, 2020 at 1530 UTC near the black line denoted in Fig. 10a. This cross section
348 is about 45 minutes after the EXRAD observations and about 25 - 50 km displacement from the
349 EXRAD flight track.

350 The model reflectivity (Fig. 8a) and vertical velocity (Fig. 8b) fields show a deep, convective
351 tower with strong vertical velocities in the boundary layer (~ 65 km along-track) that penetrate
352 to ~ 10 km height, which is similar to the EXRAD observations (Fig. 5). Beyond ~ 65 km
353 along-track, a series of convective plumes are visible in the 6 - 10 km layer with some of these

343 FIG. 8. Model vertical cross sections on 1 February, 2020 1530 UTC showing (a) reflectivity (dBZ) and (b)
 344 vertical velocity (m s^{-1}). The vertical cross section is taken close to the black line in Fig.10a. Note that the
 345 vertical velocity field is masked to the reflectivity field.

354 features disconnected from the lower-levels. The general structure of these plumes is similar to the
 355 EXRAD observations, albeit at much coarser resolution.

356 Figure 9 shows the simulated along-track and across-track winds on 1 February, 2020 at 1530
 357 UTC with data averaged $\sim \pm 5$ km across-track, which can be compared to the corresponding
 358 EXRAD observations in Fig. 6. The model along-track winds (Fig. 9a) are remarkably similar
 359 to the EXRAD observations (Fig. 6a) including the general increase in winds with height and
 360 along-track distance as well as similar values in many locations. For example, the peak along-track
 361 winds of ~ 30 m/s are found above 4 km height and at large along-track distances (~ 200 km and
 362 250 km in the EXRAD and model data, respectively) while the weakest winds of 0 - 5 m/s are
 363 found at 1 - 2 km height in both data sets. In addition, the vertical wind shear in the model (Fig. 9a)
 364 compares well with the shear in the observations (Fig. 6a), including showing the largest values of
 365 $1.2 \times 10^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ in the transition region between low and high winds at ~ 2 km height.

366 The across-track winds (Fig. 9b) have some similarities to the EXRAD data (Fig. 6b), but the
 367 observations have a much larger region of negative values extending up to higher levels. This is
 368 likely due to the different space/time offsets and orientation angle differences between the model
 369 and observational cross sections. Overall, these comparisons show that the simulations produce
 370 reasonable multi-band structure relative to the radar observations.

371 FIG. 9. Model vertical cross sections on 1 February, 2020 1530 UTC showing (a) along-track velocity (m s^{-1})
 372 overlaid with vertical wind shear (positive values in white and negative values in black; s^{-1}) and (b) across-track
 373 velocity (m s^{-1}). The data is averaged $\sim \pm 5$ km across-track similar to Fig. 6. The vertical cross section is taken
 374 close to the black line in Fig.10a. Note that the velocity fields are masked to the reflectivity field and data below
 375 1 km height is removed to assist in evaluating with the EXRAD scanning beam data.

376 Figure 10 shows the simulated reflectivity of the southern low pressure system and associated
 377 precipitation field to the north/northeast of the center in domain 1 on 1 February, 2020 at 1400
 378 UTC. The reflectivity has been filtered with a two-dimensional running mean over a 10 km x 10
 379 km box to remove grid-scale noise.

380 The low-level reflectivity (0 - 3 km height averaged; Fig. 10a) does not appear to show any
381 discernible multi-bands. Instead, a large swath of precipitation is located to the northeast of the
382 system center, displaced due to the strong environmental vertical wind shear. The line of elevated
383 precipitation oriented northeast of the point $X=200$ km, $Y=200$ km is the stationary front shown in
384 Figure 1. The horizontal wind vectors show cyclonic flow centered about the domain origin with
385 the strongest winds of ~ 20 m/s in the heavy precipitation to the northeast of the center. Figure
386 10b shows a composite of EXRAD observations between 1224 - 1342 UTC, which shows similar
387 reflectivity and cyclonic flow structure relative to the model fields in Fig. 10a. The model winds
388 show a more northerly component relative to the observations, which could be due to uncertainties
389 in the storm center estimates and time offsets, among others.

390 At middle levels (4 - 7 km height average; Fig. 10c) a few precipitation bands oriented across
391 the black line are visible, but most of these are missing at upper levels (7 - 10 km height average;
392 Fig. 10d) except one feature near $X=100$ km, $Y=100$ km.

393 Figure 11 shows the absolute vertical vorticity field at this same time averaged over the same
394 levels as in Fig. 10. The low-level (Fig. 11a) vorticity shows a solid core of cyclonic vorticity
395 near the system center as well as a strong band of vorticity that is connected with the stationary
396 front extending to the northeast. Some positive/negative oscillations in vorticity are apparent to
397 the east of the system center, but those oscillations are more visible at mid-levels (Fig. 11b) where
398 curvature is noted. At upper-levels (Fig. 11c) there are a few vorticity oscillations to the east of
399 the along-track axis that appear to have connections with the corresponding reflectivity field (Fig.
400 10c).

401 Two hours later at 1600 UTC, the same fields have changed significantly. The low-level reflectivity
402 (Fig. 12a) looks mostly similar to the previous time, but there are some indications of spiral band
403 features present to the northeast of the center. The mid-level reflectivity (Fig. 12b) shows some
404 signatures of the low-level bands, but most of the mid-level features do not have the same orientation.
405 The mid-level bands are oriented approximately perpendicular to the along-track axis that denotes
406 the axis of band propagation.

407 The upper-level reflectivity (Fig. 12c) shows narrow signatures of multi-bands that extend from
408 near the system center out to approximately 300 km radius. The wavelengths of the reflectivity
409 bands in Fig. 12 are ~ 30 km, which is very similar to those documented from the GOES data (Fig.

415 FIG. 10. Horizontal cross sections of the simulated reflectivity (dBZ) in domain 1 on 1 February, 2020 at
 416 1400 UTC. Panels (a), (c) and (d) show the 0 - 3 km, 4 - 7 km and 7 - 10 km height averaged fields, respectively.
 417 The horizontal wind vector at 1.25 km height is overlaid on panel (a) with a reference wind vector of 20 m/s.
 418 The black line in these panels denotes the along-track axis (normal to the phase lines) of multi-bands observed in
 419 subsequent figures. The gray box in (a) marks the domain showed in (b). Panel (b) shows the EXRAD observed
 420 reflectivity and horizontal wind vector at 1.25 km height between 1224 - 1342 UTC on the same date as the
 421 model panels. The reference wind vector at $X=50, Y=0$ is 20 m/s.

410 7). The horizontal wind vectors at 6 km height show strongly diffluent flow in the region of the
 411 bands, supporting their growth, as well as intense radial outflow from the system center between
 412 20 - 30 m/s. Figure 12d shows EXRAD observations between 1353 - 1449 UTC, which reveals
 413 similar banded reflectivity and flow structure (e.g., radial outflow) relative to the model fields in
 414 Fig. 12c.

426 Figure 13 shows the absolute vertical vorticity field at 1600 UTC. The low-level (Fig. 13a)
 427 vorticity shows similar structure to the field at 1400 UTC. The mid-level (Fig. 13b) vorticity shows
 428 noticeable curvature in the bands with positive/negative oscillations more prominent to the east

422 FIG. 11. Horizontal cross sections of the simulated absolute vertical vorticity (s^{-1}) in domain 1 (2.0 km grid
 423 spacing) on 1 February, 2020 at 1400 UTC. Panels (a), (b) and (c) show the 0 - 3 km, 4 - 7 km and 7 - 10 km
 424 height averaged fields, respectively. The black line in all panels denotes the along-track axis (normal to the phase
 425 lines) of multi-bands observed in subsequent figures.

429 of the along-track axis. The upper-level (Fig. 13c) vorticity field shows a vibrant multi-banded
 430 structure to the northeast of the system center with vorticity oscillations up to $\pm 1 \times 10^{-3} s^{-1}$ and
 431 wavelengths of ~ 30 km. This structure is consistent with the reflectivity field shown in Fig. 12c.

444 To examine the multi-bands more closely, the model data is output at two minute intervals and
 445 interpolated to a track-relative grid, centered on the black line in the preceding figures. In addition,
 446 the along-track (U_a) and across-track (U_x) velocities were computed on this grid,

$$U_a = u \cos(T) + v \sin(T) \quad (5)$$

432 FIG. 12. Horizontal cross sections of the simulated reflectivity (dBZ) in domain 1 on 1 February, 2020 at
 433 1600 UTC showing the southern low pressure system with embedded multi-bands. Panels (a), (b) and (c) show
 434 the 0 - 3 km, 4 - 7 km and 7 - 10 km height averaged fields, respectively. The horizontal wind vector at 6.0 km
 435 height is also shown in panel (c) with the reference vector of 20 m/s. The black line in these panels are the same
 436 as those shown in Fig. 10. The gray lines in panel (a) highlight indications of spiral bands. The gray box in (c)
 437 marks the domain showed in (d). Panel (d) shows the EXRAD observed reflectivity and horizontal wind vector
 438 at 6.0 km height between 1353 - 1449 UTC on the same date as the model panels. The reference wind vector at
 439 $X=150, Y=0$ is 20 m/s.

$$U_x = u \sin(T) - v \cos(T) \quad (6)$$

447 where u and v are the zonal and meridional velocities and T is the grid track angle of $\sim 75^\circ$.
 448 A positive along-track velocity is moving towards increasing along-track values (looking down
 449 the track), while a positive across-track velocity is moving towards increasing across-track values
 450 (from left to right looking down the track). One snapshot of the bands is shown in the next several

440 FIG. 13. Horizontal cross sections of the simulated absolute vertical vorticity (s^{-1}) in domain 1 (2.0 km grid
 441 spacing) showing the southern low pressure system with embedded multi-bands. Panels (a), (b) and (c) show the
 442 0 - 3 km, 4 - 7 km and 7 - 10 km height averaged fields, respectively. The black line in all panels denotes the
 443 along-track axis (normal to the phase lines) of multi-bands shown in Fig. 10.

451 figures. This snapshot is representative of the multi-band structure under investigation and thus,
 452 multiple snapshots are not shown.

457 Figure 14 shows vertical cross sections of the multi-bands averaged between ± 50 km across-
 458 track. Distinct oscillations in vertical vorticity (Fig. 14a) are visible in the 6 - 10 km layer that
 459 extend from $\sim 50 - 300$ km along track. Below 6 km, the vorticity pattern is not obvious, although
 460 some oscillations that are tilted down the track with height are visible in the $\sim 2 - 6$ km layer from
 461 $\sim 125 - 200$ km along-track. The vertical velocity field (Fig. 14b) shows similar oscillations to the
 462 vorticity in the 6 - 10 km layer, most apparent in the negative perturbations. The positive contours
 463 of vertical vorticity in the 6 - 10 km layer are found at the transition regions between downdrafts and

453 FIG. 14. Vertical cross sections of simulated data on 1 February, 2020 at 1530 UTC, averaged over the \pm
 454 50 km across-track range showing (a) absolute vertical vorticity and (b) vertical velocity with overlaid black
 455 contours of positive vertical vorticity using the same contour levels as panel (a). Also note that the dynamic
 456 tropopause, as defined by the 2 PVU surface, is approximately the upper bound on these plots (12 km height).

464 updrafts (in quadrature), which indicates that the vertical vorticity anomalies are generated from
 465 the tilting of horizontal vorticity into the vertical dimension. However, at the low-to-mid levels,
 466 particularly at the 75 km along-track position, regions of positive vertical vorticity are collocated
 467 with the updrafts, indicating that cyclonic vorticity associated with the ETC is being intensified
 468 through vertical stretching. The feature at 75 km along-track is part of the main rotating convective
 469 band located just northeast of the system center highlighted in Fig. 12 and Fig. 13.

470 What are the dynamics governing the oscillations observed in the upper-levels of the system?
 471 One might suspect the perturbations are gravity waves and we evaluate that potential here. The
 472 total phase speed of the bands is calculated by using the two-minute model output to track the lines
 473 of constant phase using the across-track velocity field (shown later in Fig. 17b) averaged over \pm
 474 50 km across-track and 6 - 10 km height. Tracking these phase lines resulted in mean total phase
 475 speeds of 26.67 m s^{-1} . In order to estimate the possibility of intrinsic propagation, the mean flow

476 in the direction of wave propagation must be removed from the total phase speed. The vertical
 477 cross sections of the bands (Fig. 14) clearly show that they are present within the 6 - 10 km layer.
 478 Sensitivity tests in the across-track averaging interval were performed for 100 km, 200 km and 300
 479 km track-relative grids. These tests showed that the mean along-track velocity, averaged over the
 480 appropriate across-track distance and layer were $\sim 27.0 \pm 0.5 \text{ m s}^{-1}$. Thus, the measured intrinsic
 481 phase speed of the multi-bands in this layer is $\sim 0 \text{ m s}^{-1}$.

482 For completeness, the theoretical gravity wave speed for this environment is also calculated. The
 483 dispersion relation for internal gravity waves is

$$(\omega - \bar{u}k)^2 (k^2 + m^2) - N^2 k^2 = 0 \quad (7)$$

484 where ω is the angular frequency, \bar{u} is the large-scale, averaged horizontal windspeed in the
 485 direction of wave propagation, N is the Brunt-Väisälä frequency, k is the horizontal wavenumber,
 486 and m is the vertical wavenumber.

487 Rearranging Eq. (7) for the intrinsic horizontal phase speed on the left-hand-side yields

$$\omega/k - \bar{u} = N/\sqrt{k^2 + m^2}. \quad (8)$$

488 The right-hand-side of Eq. (8) is evaluated using the data from the simulation. Note that the
 489 buoyancy frequency was estimated to be 50 times larger than the Coriolis frequency and thus, the
 490 potential gravity waves are not significantly affected by the Earth's rotation. Taking an average
 491 of data over the system at two different time periods and in the 6 - 10 km layer produced values
 492 of N around 10^{-2} s^{-1} . The dominant horizontal wavelength in the model is $\sim 30 \text{ km}$ and the
 493 vertical wavelength is taken to be twice the depth of the perturbations (e.g., Alexander et al.
 494 1995; Piani et al. 2000), which equates to about 8 km (verified with Fourier analysis, albeit with
 495 uncertainties). Entering these numbers produces a horizontal phase speed of 12.30 m s^{-1} , which is
 496 representative of the bands propagating down the track-relative grid to the northeast of the system
 497 center. Uncertainties in the wavelengths and buoyancy frequency were tested, which produced
 498 uncertainties in the phase speed of up to 3 m/s.

499 To solidify the results from the phase speed calculations, analysis of the internal gravity wave
 500 polarization relations were also examined. Given the linearized, Boussinesq equations of motion

501 for two-dimensional flow and inserting plane wave solutions for the perturbation variables, one
 502 arrives at the following equation,

$$\theta' = -\frac{i w' \partial \bar{\theta}}{\omega \partial z} \quad (9)$$

503 where θ is the potential temperature, w is the vertical velocity, i is the imaginary unit and the
 504 overbar represents the mean or environmental conditions. Equation (9) implies there must be a
 505 90° phase shift between the potential temperature and vertical velocity fields for features to be
 506 classified as internal gravity waves.

507 Figure 15a shows the perturbation (relative to the 50 km along-track filtered fields) potential
 508 temperature and vertical velocity fields at ~ 8 km height (center of the multi-band layer) at 1530
 509 UTC. The perturbations are within amplitudes of ± 0.5 and appear to show oscillations that are
 510 in-phase. The magnitude-squared coherence, which quantifies the linear correlation between the
 511 fields as a function of wavenumber can be written

$$C_{\theta'w'}(k) = \frac{|G_{\theta'w'}(k)|^2}{G_{\theta'\theta'}(k) G_{w'w'}(k)} \quad (10)$$

512 where $G_{\theta'w'}(k)$ denotes the cross-spectral density between θ' and w' , representing their
 513 wavenumber-dependent covariance, while $|G_{\theta'w'}(k)|^2$ is the squared magnitude of the cross-
 514 spectrum and measures the shared spectral power. The quantities $G_{\theta'\theta'}(k)$ and $G_{w'w'}(k)$ are
 515 the auto-spectral densities of θ' and w' , respectively, and represent the total power of each signal
 516 at wavenumber k . The power spectral densities are estimated using the periodogram method with
 517 a Hamming window length set to three times the largest expected wavelength in the data, which
 518 divides the signals into about four segments. There is some sensitivity in the structure of the
 519 resulting plot to the window length, but not in the main results.

520 The perturbation potential temperature and vertical velocity fields are input to the calculation
 521 described above and the results are shown in Fig. 15b. A peak in the coherence is found at ~ 0.2
 522 radians/km, which translates to a wavelength of ~ 30 km. This wavelength is consistent with the
 523 scale of the multi-bands in the simulation mentioned previously as well as the GOES observations.
 524 Other peaks in the coherence occur at high wavenumbers and are not associated with the features

531 FIG. 15. Signal processing analysis of the oscillations in the numerical simulation at 1530 UTC showing
 532 (a) perturbation potential temperature and vertical velocity at ~ 8 km height averaged over the ± 50 km across-
 533 track range, (b) the magnitude-squared coherence estimate of the two variables shown in (a) as a function of
 534 wavenumber and (c) the phase lags between the two variables shown in (a) as a function of wavenumber.

525 under investigation. The phase lag between the perturbation fields is shown in Fig.15c and is
 526 computed as $\phi_{\theta', w'}(k) = \arg(G_{\theta', w'}(k))$ using the same periodogram method.

527 Focusing on the dominant wavelength, the phase lag at ~ 0.2 radians/km is close to 0, which
 528 means the perturbation potential temperature and vertical velocity oscillations are in-phase. This
 529 result is consistent with the manual inspection of the waves in Fig. 15a and is robust for different
 530 height levels within the 6 - 10 km layer and for different time periods.

535 *It is clear from these calculations that the measured intrinsic phase speeds and phase rela-*
 536 *tionships in key variables have a large mismatch with the theoretical intrinsic phase speeds and*
 537 *polarization relations for internal gravity waves, even with significant uncertainty bounds in various*
 538 *parameters. Thus, the observed multi-bands in the upper-levels cannot be gravity waves.*

539 However, there are more subtle oscillations in several variables in the low to middle levels of the
 540 system that are revealed through examining the perturbation fields (deviations from 50 km running
 541 mean values). The perturbation vertical velocity at 1530 UTC (Fig. 16a) shows the prominent
 542 multi-bands in the 6 - 10 km layer along with weaker perturbations in the $\sim 0 - 6$ km layer denoted by
 543 black arrows. The weaker oscillations exhibit amplitudes approximately three to four times lower
 544 than those in the upper layer, making them clearly distinguishable despite the similar wavelengths

FIG. 16. The same as Fig. 14 only showing (a) perturbation vertical velocity (m s^{-1}) and (b) perturbation reflectivity (dBZ). The black arrows in panel (a) denote features discussed in the text.

545 of ~ 30 km. Animations of vertical velocity (not shown) appear to show these waves emanating
 546 from the deep convection present at ~ 75 km along-track. The perturbation reflectivity (Fig. 16b)
 547 is largely consistent with the vertical velocity except the low to middle level oscillations are about
 548 ten times lower in amplitude than the upper layer waves. This is why the multi-bands are not as
 549 visible in the low-level precipitation field as shown by the reflectivity (Fig. 12a).

550 The low to middle level waves (0 - 6 km layer) were tracked in the perturbation vertical velocity
 551 field with the two minute model output and the total phase speeds were measured. This procedure
 552 produced total wave phase speeds of $\sim 30 \pm 3$ m/s. The along-track velocity was averaged across-
 553 track (± 50 km), along-track (0 - 342 km) and height (0 - 6 km) to represent the mean flow moving
 554 the waves, which resulted in values of $\sim 14 \pm 0.5$ m/s. Thus, the measured intrinsic phase speeds of
 555 the waves were ~ 16 m/s. The theoretical intrinsic phase speeds for gravity waves were computed
 556 using the same inputs as before with the exception of a 12 km vertical wavelength. These inputs
 557 produced values of 17.73 m/s, which is close to the measured intrinsic phase speed of ~ 16 m/s.

560 FIG. 17. The same as Fig. 14 only showing (a) along-track velocity (m s^{-1}) overlaid with vertical wind shear
 561 (positive values in white and negative values in black; s^{-1}) and (b) across-track velocity (m s^{-1}) overlaid with
 562 perturbation wind vectors in the plane of the cross-section. The reference vectors in the top right of panel (b) are
 563 2 m/s (along-track) and 0.5 m/s (vertical). Several example circulation patterns are highlighted with gray lines.

568 *Thus, these low to middle level waves can be identified as internal gravity waves that are being*
 569 *generated by the convective activity closer to the system center.*

564 If the dominant, upper-level multi-bands are not gravity waves, what is driving their dynamics?
 565 Figure 17 shows vertical cross sections of the along-track velocity and across-track velocity. The
 566 along-track velocity (Fig. 17a) shows a jet centered at ~ 11 km height with large values of vertical
 567 shear (maximum values of 0.01 s^{-1}) located between 8 - 10 km height and most notably between
 568 50 - 225 km along-track. The locations of the large vertical wind shear values match well with
 569 the locations of the wave motions associated with the multi-bands. For example, the across-track
 570 velocity (Fig. 17b) reveals clear wave motions in the 6 - 10 km layer and between 50 - 250 km
 571 along-track.

572 The perturbation wind vectors show counter-rotating secondary circulations in this region, some
 573 of which are highlighted in Fig. 17b. These secondary circulations are deforming the across-

574 track velocity field into wave motions with the upward and downward branches causing growth of
575 the wave ridges and troughs, respectively. The counter-rotating circulations combine to produce
576 enhanced updrafts and downdrafts, with associated reflectivity perturbations (Fig. 16b), that look
577 very similar to “boundary layer rolls” or “cloud streets” (e.g., Young et al. 2002; Morrison et al.
578 2005). There are perhaps extensions of the wave motions down to $\sim 4 - 5$ km in some regions, but
579 overall, the oscillations become less detectable below 6 km height. Note that the structure shown
580 in Fig. 17 is not isolated to this particular time, but is representative of a larger time window where
581 the multi-bands are active.

582 The along-track and across-track velocity fields shown in Fig. 17 match well with the EXRAD
583 observations shown in Fig. 6, despite the differences in spatial/temporal coverage. In the along-
584 track velocity field, both the observations (Fig. 6a) and model (Fig. 17a) show the same structure
585 and similar magnitudes with large changes in the winds at lower levels. Of course, the upper-level
586 jet is not observed in the EXRAD data due to the lack of scattering at this level. The structure of
587 the across-track velocity field is also similar in both the observations (Fig. 6b) and model (Fig.
588 17b).

589 Figure 18 shows the gradient Richardson number,

$$\text{Ri} = \frac{(g/\theta) \partial\theta/\partial z}{(\partial u/\partial z)^2 + (\partial v/\partial z)^2}, \quad (11)$$

590 at two time periods during the evolution of the multi-bands. At early time periods (1402 UTC; Fig.
591 18a), before the bands become prominent, the wave motions are more pronounced closer to the
592 system center ($\sim 0 - 150$ km along-track) with large amplitude waves centered at 25 km and 100 km
593 along-track. The Richardson number is less than 0.75 and 0.25 at the crests of these wave motions
594 over significant distances. Note that average Richardson numbers ± 10 km across-track are used to
595 represent some of the spatial domain covered by the bands. However, larger averaging domains can
596 affect the presented values and the interpretation of dynamic stability and turbulent flow. While
597 the critical value for dynamic instability and turbulence has traditionally been 0.25, values up to
598 0.75 are shown since there can be considerable variability in this threshold (e.g., Galperin et al.
599 2007).

600 At later time periods (1548 UTC; Fig. 18b), when the bands are mature, the wave motions are
601 prominent throughout the entire along-track domain. The amplitude of these wave motions gets

602 larger with along-track distance. Low Richardson number values, down to 0.25 and below, are
 603 again found at the crests of the waves, for the most part. Notably, the low Richardson number
 604 values are found in the 6 - 10 km layer and across the full span of the along-track axis, which is
 605 consistent with all other wave diagnostics shown in this paper.

606 FIG. 18. Vertical cross sections of cross-track velocity (m/s) overlaid with the gradient Richardson number
 607 in white contours, averaged over the ± 10 km across-track range on 1 February, 2020 at (a) 1402 UTC and (b)
 608 1548 UTC.

609 *The analysis of Figs. 17 and 18 indicates that hydrodynamic instability through vertical wind*
 610 *shear is the likely source of the wave motions and associated secondary circulations.*¹ The specific
 611 type of instability is likely dominated by inflection-point instability (Brown 1972), given the
 612 structure of the counter-rotating circulations, with Kelvin-Helmholtz instability potentially playing
 613 a secondary role. *This is a new finding to explain the mechanisms behind precipitation multi-bands*
 614 *observed in ETCs, at least those bands that are found in the mid to upper levels of these systems.*
 615 *Furthermore, this explanation is consistent with the EXRAD observations shown in Fig. 5, which*

¹For completeness, the conditions for CSI were examined in the multi-bands following Schultz and Schumacher (1999). This analysis showed that CSI is not a viable mechanism to explain the multi-bands because the circulations were dominated by conditional gravitational instability, with additional patches where CSI was entirely absent.

616 *show mid-to-upper level plumes that are de-coupled from the surface.* However, additional work is
617 needed to understand these instabilities further and extend these results to a wide variety of cases.

618 Previous studies of ETCs have noted radar signatures that are indicative of Kelvin–Helmholtz
619 instability and explored their microphysical implications (Houser and Bluestein 2011; Medina
620 and Houze 2016; Barnes et al. 2018). However, these studies did not rule out gravity waves as
621 a potential explanation for these features, nor have they addressed the dynamics underlying the
622 formation of multi-bands. In addition, the oscillations identified in these previous studies had
623 wavelengths of ~ 5 km, which are significantly smaller than those waves documented here.

624 FIG. 19. Horizontal wind speed (m/s) in storm-centered coordinates at ~ 12 km height (near the tropopause
625 as defined by the 2 PVU surface) overlaid with the mean wind vector in the 6 - 10 km layer on 1 February, 2020
626 averaged between 1400 - 1600 UTC. The black line denotes the along-track axis (normal to the phase lines) of
627 the multi-bands.

628 It is very difficult to separate the upper-level flow contributions from the mid-latitude jet and
629 convectively forced outflow. Figure 19 shows the mid-latitude jet to the west/southwest (air moving
630 to the east/northeast) of the system center averaged between 1400 - 1600 UTC. The wind speed
631 maximum to the northeast of the system center appears to have some connection to the mid-latitude
632 jet, but perturbations to this larger-scale structure are visible due to convective activity. The multi-
633 bands are oriented at an oblique angle relative to the jet axis as shown by the along-track axis

634 labeled in Fig. 19. This suggests that the synoptic scale forcing is not the sole driver of the vertical
635 shear instabilities. There is also a significant across-track component to the mean wind vector in
636 the 6 - 10 km layer, which is parallel to the phase lines of the multi-bands. However, a component
637 of the mean wind vector is pointing down the along-track axis with an average angle of $\sim 30^\circ$. This
638 characteristic is necessary to produce the secondary circulations shown in Fig.17b and strongly
639 supports the presence of perturbations driven by inflection-point instabilities (Brown 1972; Young
640 et al. 2002).

641 **6. Summary and conclusions**

642 In this paper, the fundamental dynamics governing the evolution of multi-bands in ETCs was
643 studied through a detailed case study from the IMPACTS campaign. This is an important problem
644 given the impacts multi-bands have on the precipitation field, especially snow, and the poor forecast
645 ability of current predictive models.

646 Between ~ 1200 and 1800 UTC on 1 February, 2020, GOES-16 visible satellite images showed
647 deep convective cells firing on the down-shear side of the storm near the core as the cyclone emerged
648 off of North Carolina near the Gulf Stream. These convective cells appeared to generate narrow
649 oscillations in the cloud field that propagated away from the system center with time. In addition
650 to the localized convective cells, the visible satellite images also showed elongated multi-bands
651 of cloud that persisted for longer periods of time. Vertical cross sections of those bands from the
652 EXRAD instrument on the NASA ER-2 aircraft showed deep convection closer to the system core
653 along with reflectivity plumes in the $\sim 5 - 10$ km layer associated with the multi-bands. Vertical
654 velocity retrievals showed the plume updrafts were concentrated in the mid-to-upper levels and did
655 not extend to the lower levels.

656 Wavelet analysis on the satellite data showed the multi-bands have a central wavelength of ~ 30
657 km. Weaker regions of power at a scale of $15 - 20$ km are representative of the narrow oscillations
658 associated with deep convection. These smaller-scale features have a lifecycle of ~ 30 minutes
659 while the larger-scale bands persist for several hours. The smaller-scale bands were shown to exist
660 in the vicinity of the dominant bands with merging also apparent.

661 Several excellent papers have been published in the literature proposing mechanisms for the
662 formation and evolution of multi-bands as described in the introduction section. A central theory

663 for the explanation of multi-bands is that they are gravity waves generated from convection and/or
664 flow imbalance (see Ruppert et al. (2022) for a review). However, the dominant multi-bands
665 presented in this study (wavelengths of ~ 30 km; found in the 6 - 10 km layer in multiple variables)
666 from both observational and model data do not validate with gravity wave theory as demonstrated
667 by the intrinsic phase speed and polarization relation calculations.

668 Instead, the bands are shown to be associated with strong vertical wind shear just below the peak
669 in the upper-level outflow (~ 11 km) with low Richardson numbers, especially in the crests of
670 the oscillations. In addition, the perturbation flow in the across-band dimension showed counter-
671 rotating secondary circulations within the multi-bands that are acting to build the ridge and dig
672 the trough of the waves shown in the across-track velocity field. The secondary circulations are
673 combining to produce enhanced updrafts and downdrafts that are consistent with the reflectivity
674 perturbations. These results indicate that the observed multi-band structures arise from hydro-
675 dynamic instabilities, with inflection-point instability representing the dominant mechanism and
676 Kelvin–Helmholtz instability potentially contributing as a secondary effect.

677 The following physical interpretation is hypothesized to explain the presence of the instability.
678 The convective cells identified in the observations and model eventually consolidated into a larger
679 convective mass and associated cyclonic vorticity anomaly, which are shown by the model reflec-
680 tivity and vorticity fields, respectively. Through mass continuity, this convective growth likely
681 enhanced the upper-level outflow of the system, thereby increasing the localized vertical wind
682 shear just below the jet maximum. At the same time, internal gravity waves, identified in the
683 low to mid levels of the system and verified with phase speed calculations, are coming off of the
684 convection located closer to the storm core. These waves propagated radially outward and upward
685 with time, as observed through animated model fields, with wavelengths of ~ 30 km. Thus, it is
686 reasonable to assume that the multi-band structures may have been triggered by the gravity waves.
687 However, the shear instabilities are the fundamental mechanism for the presence and evolution of
688 the multi-bands.

689 This physical interpretation is consistent with the intensification of the surface low pressure
690 by ~ 7 hPa from 1200 to 1800 UTC, which covers the period under investigation. Tests of
691 this hypothesized chain of events would require idealized modeling to isolate the impact of the
692 convective activity and gravity waves on the shear instability and is left for future work.

693 Perturbations in the model reflectivity, vertical velocity and vertical vorticity fields are found in
694 the mid-to-upper levels of the system associated with the secondary circulations. Perturbations in
695 these variables are seen in the low-to-mid levels as well, but with much weaker amplitudes (by
696 a factor of 3 - 10). Thus, while connections of the multi-bands to the surface precipitation field
697 are apparent, they are not strong enough in the present case to develop clear perturbations in the
698 reflectivity field. Future work should examine a wide variety of systems, especially stronger cases
699 that display clear multi-bands in the surface precipitation field, to examine the robustness of these
700 results.

701 *Acknowledgments.* The IMPACTS field campaign and the work of author Guimond are supported
702 by the NASA Earth Venture Suborbital (EVS) program and NASA grant 80NSSC24K0302. Author
703 Guimond thanks the IMPACTS team members for organizing the campaign, providing forecasting
704 support, coordinating the flights and collecting the data. Many thanks are given to Dr. Paul Reasor
705 for multiple discussions on the work that improved this paper considerably. Feedback on the gravity
706 wave analysis from Dr. Steven Koch is also greatly appreciated. Finally, author Guimond thanks
707 three anonymous reviewers for their extensive comments and constructive criticism.

708 *Data availability statement.* The data sets needed to reproduce the core results of this paper can
709 be found at the following link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17253490>

710 **References**

711 Alexander, M. J., J. R. Holton, and D. R. Durran, 1995: The gravity wave response above deep
712 convection in a squall line simulation. *Journal of the Atmospheric Sciences*, **52**, 2212–2226.

713 Barnes, H. C., J. P. Zagrodnik, L. A. McMurdie, A. K. Rowe, and J. Houze, R. A., 2018:
714 Kelvin–helmholtz waves in precipitating midlatitude cyclones. *Journal of the Atmospheric Sci-*
715 *ences*, **75 (8)**, 2763–2785, <https://doi.org/10.1175/JAS-D-17-0365.1>.

716 Bosart, L. F., W. E. Bracken, and A. Seimon, 1998: A study of cyclone mesoscale structure with em-
717 phasis on a large-amplitude inertia–gravity wave. *Monthly Weather Review*, **126 (6)**, 1497–1527,
718 [https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0493\(1998\)126<1497:ASOCMS>2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0493(1998)126<1497:ASOCMS>2.0.CO;2), URL [https://journals.](https://journals.ametsoc.org/view/journals/mwre/126/6/1520-0493_1998_126_1497_asocms_2.0.co_2.xml)
719 [ametsoc.org/view/journals/mwre/126/6/1520-0493_1998_126_1497_asocms_2.0.co_2.xml](https://journals.ametsoc.org/view/journals/mwre/126/6/1520-0493_1998_126_1497_asocms_2.0.co_2.xml).

720 Brown, R. A., 1972: On the inflection point instability of a stratified ekman boundary layer.
721 *Journal of the Atmospheric Sciences*, **29 (5)**, 850–859, [https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0469\(1972\)](https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0469(1972)029<0850:OTIPIO>2.0.CO;2)
722 [029<0850:OTIPIO>2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0469(1972)029<0850:OTIPIO>2.0.CO;2).

723 Galperin, B., S. Sukoriansky, and P. S. Anderson, 2007: On the critical richardson number in stably
724 stratified turbulence. *Atmospheric Science Letters*, **8 (3)**, 65–69, <https://doi.org/10.1002/asl.153>,
725 URL <https://doi.org/10.1002/asl.153>.

726 Ganetis, S. A., B. A. Colle, S. E. Yuter, and N. P. Hoban, 2018: Environmental conditions
727 associated with observed snowband structures within northeast u.s. winter storms. *Mon. Wea.*
728 *Rev.*, **146**, 3675–3690, <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1175/MWR-D-18-0054.1>.

- 729 Guimond, S., 2023: Er-2 x-band radar (extrad) 3d winds impacts. NASA Global Hydrometeorol-
730 ogy Resource Center DAAC, Huntsville, Alabama, U.S.A., URL [http://dx.doi.org/10.5067/](http://dx.doi.org/10.5067/IMPACTS/EXRAD/DATA201)
731 [IMPACTS/EXRAD/DATA201](http://dx.doi.org/10.5067/IMPACTS/EXRAD/DATA201), dataset available online, [https://doi.org/10.5067/IMPACTS/](https://doi.org/10.5067/IMPACTS/EXRAD/DATA201)
732 [EXRAD/DATA201](https://doi.org/10.5067/IMPACTS/EXRAD/DATA201).
- 733 Guimond, S. R., J. M. Reisner, S. Marras, and F. X. Giraldo, 2016: The impacts of dry dynamic
734 cores on asymmetric hurricane intensification. *Journal of the Atmospheric Sciences*, **73** (12),
735 4661–4684, <https://doi.org/10.1175/JAS-D-16-0055.1>.
- 736 Guimond, S. R., S. Sroka, and D. Protzko, 2018: A large eddy simulation of hurricane inten-
737 sification. *33rd Conference on Hurricanes and Tropical Meteorology*, American Meteorolog-
738 ical Society, 17, URL [https://science.gsfc.nasa.gov/sed/content/uploadFiles/publication_files/](https://science.gsfc.nasa.gov/sed/content/uploadFiles/publication_files/large_eddy_33hurr_guimond.pdf)
739 [large_eddy_33hurr_guimond.pdf](https://science.gsfc.nasa.gov/sed/content/uploadFiles/publication_files/large_eddy_33hurr_guimond.pdf), available online.
- 740 Guimond, S. R., L. Tian, G. M. Heymsfield, and S. J. Frasier, 2014: Wind Retrieval Algo-
741 rithms for the IWRAP and HIWRAP Airborne Doppler Radars with Applications to Hurri-
742 canes. *Journal of Atmospheric and Oceanic Technology*, **31** (6), 1189–1215, [https://doi.org/](https://doi.org/10.1175/JTECH-D-13-00140.1)
743 [10.1175/JTECH-D-13-00140.1](https://doi.org/10.1175/JTECH-D-13-00140.1).
- 744 Heymsfield, G. M., L. Tian, A. J. Heymsfield, L. Li, and S. Guimond, 2009: Characteristics of deep
745 tropical and subtropical convection from nadir-viewing high-altitude airborne doppler radar.
746 *Journal of the Atmospheric Sciences*, **67**, 285–308, <https://doi.org/10.1175/2009JAS3132.1>,
747 submitted March 2009, revised June 2009.
- 748 Houser, J. L., and H. B. Bluestein, 2011: Polarimetric doppler radar observations of kelvin–
749 helmholtz waves in a winter storm. *Journal of the Atmospheric Sciences*, **68** (7), 1676–1702,
750 <https://doi.org/10.1175/2011JAS3566.1>.
- 751 Koch, S. E., and L. M. Siedlarz, 1999: Mesoscale gravity waves and their environment in the
752 central united states during storm-fest. *Mon. Wea. Rev.*, **127**, 2854–2879, [https://doi.org/https://doi.org/](https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0493(1999)127%3C2854:MGWATE%3E2.0.CO;2)
753 [https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0493\(1999\)127%3C2854:MGWATE%3E2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0493(1999)127%3C2854:MGWATE%3E2.0.CO;2).
- 754 Lindzen, R., and K. Tung, 1976: Banded convective activity and ducted gravity waves. *Mon. Wea.*
755 *Rev.*, **104**, 1602–1617, [https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0493\(1976\)104\(1602:BCAADG\)2.0.CO;](https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0493(1976)104(1602:BCAADG)2.0.CO;2)
756 [2.](https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0493(1976)104(1602:BCAADG)2.0.CO;2)

- 757 Liu, Y., X. San Liang, and R. H. Weisberg, 2007: Rectification of the bias in the wavelet power
758 spectrum. *Journal of Atmospheric and Oceanic Technology*, **24** (12), 2093–2102, [https://doi.org/](https://doi.org/10.1175/2007JTECHO511.1)
759 10.1175/2007JTECHO511.1.
- 760 McMurdie, L., and Coauthors, 2022: Chasing snowstorms: The investigation of microphysics and
761 precipitation for atlantic coast-threatening snowstorms (impacts) campaign. *Bull. Amer. Meteor.*
762 *Soc.*, **103**, E1243–E1269, <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1175/BAMS-D-20-0246.1>.
- 763 Medina, S., and J. Houze, R. A., 2016: Kelvin-helmholtz waves in extratropical cyclones passing
764 over mountain ranges. *Quarterly Journal of the Royal Meteorological Society*, **142** (697), 1311–
765 1319, <https://doi.org/10.1002/qj.2755>.
- 766 Morrison, I., S. Businger, F. Marks, P. Dodge, and J. A. Businger, 2005: An observational case
767 for the prevalence of roll vortices in the hurricane boundary layer. *Journal of the Atmospheric*
768 *Sciences*, **62** (8), 2662–2673, <https://doi.org/10.1175/JAS3508.1>.
- 769 Piani, C., D. R. Durran, M. J. Alexander, and J. R. Holton, 2000: A numerical study of three-
770 dimensional gravity waves triggered by deep tropical convection and their role in the dynamics
771 of the qbo. *Journal of the Atmospheric Sciences*, **57** (22), 3689–3702.
- 772 Protzko, D. E., S. R. Guimond, C. R. Jackson, J. W. Sapp, Z. Jelenak, and P. S. Chang, 2023:
773 Documenting coherent turbulent structures in the boundary layer of intense hurricanes through
774 wavelet analysis on iwrap and sar data. *IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing*,
775 **61**, 1–16, <https://doi.org/10.1109/TGRS.2023.3305998>.
- 776 Ruppert, J. H., S. E. Koch, X. Chen, Y. Du, A. Seimon, Y. Q. Sun, J. Wei, and L. F.
777 Bosart, 2022: Mesoscale gravity waves and midlatitude weather: A tribute to fuqing
778 zhang. *Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society*, **103** (1), E129–E156, [https://doi.org/](https://doi.org/10.1175/BAMS-D-20-0005.1)
779 10.1175/BAMS-D-20-0005.1.
- 780 Schultz, D. M., and P. N. Schumacher, 1999: The use and misuse of conditional symmetric instabil-
781 ity. *Mon. Wea. Rev.*, **127**, 2709–2732, [https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0493\(1999\)](https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0493(1999)127,2709:TUAMOC.2.0.CO;2)
782 127,2709:TUAMOC.2.0.CO;2.
- 783 Skamarock, W. C., and Coauthors, 2019: A description of the advanced research wrf version 4.

784 Tech. Rep. NCAR/TN-556+STR, National Center for Atmospheric Research, Boulder, Colorado,
785 145 pp. pp. <https://doi.org/10.5065/1dfh-6p97>, URL <https://doi.org/10.5065/1dfh-6p97>.

786 Torrence, C., and G. P. Compo, 1998: A practical guide to wavelet analysis. *Bulletin of the Ameri-*
787 *can Meteorological Society*, **79** (1), 61–78, [https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0477\(1998\)079<0061:](https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0477(1998)079<0061:APGTWA>2.0.CO;2)
788 [APGTWA](https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0477(1998)079<0061:APGTWA>2.0.CO;2)>2.0.CO;2.

789 Uccellini, L. W., and S. E. Koch, 1987: The synoptic setting and possible energy sources for
790 mesoscale wave disturbances. *Mon. Wea. Rev.*, **115**, 721–729, [https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.](https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0493(1987)115%3C0721:TSSAPE%3E2.0.CO;2)
791 [1175/1520-0493\(1987\)115%3C0721:TSSAPE%3E2.0.CO;2](https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0493(1987)115%3C0721:TSSAPE%3E2.0.CO;2).

792 Ulbrich, C. W., and P. B. Chilson, 1994: Effects of variations in precipitation size distribution
793 and fallspeed law parameters on relations between mean doppler fallspeed and reflectivity
794 factor. *Journal of Atmospheric and Oceanic Technology*, **11**, 1656–1663, [https://doi.org/10.](https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0426(1994)011<1656:EOVIPS>2.0.CO;2)
795 [1175/1520-0426\(1994\)011<1656:EOVIPS](https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0426(1994)011<1656:EOVIPS>2.0.CO;2)>2.0.CO;2.

796 Walker McLinden, M. L. W., A. M. Loftus, L. Li, and G. M. Heymsfield, 2021: Ap-
797 plication of nonuniform beam filling (nubf) doppler velocity error correction on airborne
798 radar measurements. *IEEE Geoscience and Remote Sensing Letters*, **19**, 1–5, [https://doi.org/](https://doi.org/10.1109/LGRS.2021.3120647)
799 [10.1109/LGRS.2021.3120647](https://doi.org/10.1109/LGRS.2021.3120647).

800 Xu, Q., 1989: Frontal circulations in the presence of small viscous moist symmetric stability and
801 weak forcing. *Quart. J. Roy. Meteor. Soc.*, **115**, 1325–1353.

802 Xu, Q., 1992: Formation and evolution of frontal rainbands and geostrophic potential vor-
803 ticity anomalies. *Journal of the Atmospheric Sciences*, **49** (8), 629–648, [https://doi.org/](https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0469(1992)049<0629:FAEOFR>2.0.CO;2)
804 [10.1175/1520-0469\(1992\)049<0629:FAEOFR](https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0469(1992)049<0629:FAEOFR>2.0.CO;2)>2.0.CO;2.

805 Young, G. S., D. A. R. Kristovich, M. R. Hjelmfelt, and R. C. Foster, 2002: Rolls, streets, waves,
806 and more: A review of quasi-two-dimensional structures in the atmospheric boundary layer.
807 *Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society*, **83** (7), 997–1001, [https://doi.org/10.1175/](https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0477(2002)083<0997:RSWAMA>2.3.CO;2)
808 [1520-0477\(2002\)083<0997:RSWAMA](https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0477(2002)083<0997:RSWAMA>2.3.CO;2)>2.3.CO;2.

809 Zhang, F., C. Davis, M. Kaplan, and S. Koch, 2001: Wavelet analysis and the governing dynamics
810 of a large-amplitude mesoscale gravity-wave event along the east coast of the united states. *Q.J.R.*
811 *Meteorol. Soc.*, **127**, 2209–2245, <https://doi.org/10.1002/qj.49712757702>.